

ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Annotation. Independent study is a serious contender for a fundamental change in all higher education. The depth of this change is determined by trends in the use of technology, in the revision of the relationship between teacher and students, and in the emergence of new types of teacher activities.

Key words. Distance learning, higher education system, ability, teacher activities, technologies, methods, credit-module system

The Concept of Development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for the introduction of educational programs aimed at developing students' creative thinking and practical skills based on individual educational trajectories.

For the third year, starting from the 2020-2021 academic year, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been gradually transferring the educational process of higher educational institutions to a credit-module system. "Credit – module training provides for an increase in the proportion of hours devoted to self-education, implementation methods and technologies aimed at developing students' skills of independent education, critical and creative thinking, system analysis, entrepreneurial skills, the introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process." In this regard, the efforts of many educational theorists and practitioners are currently focused on the use of interactive technologies in organizing the student's independent work. The development of students' independent work serves as a driving force for the progressive reform of vocational education, the transition from the reproductive

form to the active development of knowledge, to education based on the active and constructive joint activity of the teacher and the student.

Independent study is a serious contender for a fundamental change in all higher education. The depth of this change is determined by trends in the use of technology, in the revision of the relationship between teacher and students, and in the emergence of new types of teacher activities.

The current situation in the education system offers educational institutions an unprecedented opportunity to create an educational environment where technology will primarily focus on the needs of students. Moving away from monologue as a traditionally prevailing form of educational activity, the development of such a form of learning as polylogue (communication, conversation, discussion); understanding foreign language communication not only as the ability to clothe information in the structure and forms of the foreign language, but also as a partner's motivation to some kind of action of a verbal and non-verbal order, as well as the realization of self-expression the speaker; understanding knowledge not as impersonal information, but as a set the skills actualized in the system of the subject's activity are all the main tasks of organizing independent work of students in learning the foreign language.

To accomplish these tasks, it is necessary to develop students' communicative competence, i.e. the ability to extract sufficiently complete information when reading texts in foreign language, the ability to understand the interlocutor, as well as express their thoughts, points of view orally and in writing. It is known that the peculiarity of learning the foreign language is not so much knowledge about the subject itself, i.e. about the language (language competence), as the development of certain skills and abilities of different types of speech activity based on knowledge about the mode of activity (communicative competence).

The type of activity is possible only during the performance of this activity. It follows that when teaching the foreign language, it is necessary to organize

independent actions students (and each student) in the kind of speech activity that they are taught. If students are taught to read, then each student should be given the opportunity to read and practice reading. When teaching speaking, each student should be given the opportunity to speak and express their thoughts in other language. When learning listening, every student should have the opportunity to listen to foreign language speech. It is important to keep in mind the existing pattern, formulated at the time by the famous methodologist I.V. Rakhmanov: the basis of learning any kind of speech activity are auditory-motor skills, therefore, oral practice is necessary in the formation of skills for any kind of speech activity. Distance learning based on computer telecommunications is very effective for organizing such work. Distance learning in the foreign language has its own specifics, due to the fact that it involves teaching various types of speech activity. Naturally, for teaching such types of speech activity as reading and writing, one can largely limit oneself to a network course, since the features of these types of speech activity do not require voluminous graphics and even significant sound accompaniment. However, when teaching pronunciation, speech and listening, it is not possible to limit oneself to text files only, it is necessary to rely on sound accompaniment, as well as the creation of various situations that stimulate oral communication statements of the trainees, i.e. there is a need to rely on illustrative material. Using such material in online courses, as we already know, is technically quite possible, but in practice, given the real situation, it is still quite problematic due to the large amount of memory that such files require. However, technological mobility is the possibility of using elements of the environment in various distance learning technologies used in universities, including in the systems "case-DO" (a course of study on printed media, which may include audio cassettes), "tele-DO" (a video training course with additional printed materials) and "Internet-DO" (computer programs, e-mail, Internet) It is now available to many universities.

As practice shows, a significant proportion of the population of Uzbekistan currently has a sufficient level of technical equipment for the consumption of

educational services of high-tech distance learning, including, based on Internet technologies that can provide maximum interactivity and therefore are the most preferred for the consumer market. A prerequisite for the effective use of these technological capabilities is high-quality information content that supports the process of distance learning and educational process management. In our classes, we analyzed the rationality of using the latest technologies in teaching foreign language at a higher educational institution. In our opinion, Computer-based learning has the greatest effect when students are involved in active cognitive activity to comprehend and consolidate educational material, apply knowledge in the course of solving problems. Computer training programs of this type present tasks of training exercises to an independently studying student, evaluate their performance, provide prompt assistance in the form of hints, explanations of typical errors, and presentation of appropriate theoretical material. Therefore, one of the most important areas of independent work of students at non-philological faculties is the creation of a unified learning environment and their own licensed training program. In this case, the program should include as a basic the level of grammar, phonetics, vocabulary, listening skills for beginners to learn foreign language, as well as an advanced level for undergraduates, including journalistic articles, not adapted texts, audio recordings of native speakers language and simultaneous translation functions. For the use of computer programs, the group can be divided as follows: the 1st group - the largest percentage of interested students, the 2nd group – those who expressed their commitment to traditional types of education. According to the results of the final control, group 1 showed the highest quality level of assimilation of the material. Orientation on the Internet, search speed and instant application of the learned material in practice have significantly increased their rating. Subsequently the 2nd group also expressed a desire to continue using computer programs in training.

Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the further development of information technologies, the integration of distance education will lead distance

learning to the status of the most widely used method, which can provide maximum interactivity and therefore will be the most preferred in the field of education.

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